

ETHICAL-AESTHETIC IN LEADING STAFF CONCEPTUAL BASIS OF CULTURE DEVELOPMENT AND MODERN APPROACHES

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Annotation In the article, it is stated that one of the urgent tasks is to educate the management staff on the basis of the honesty vaccine, the tasks aimed at forming honesty and fair functioning skills in the management staff by developing ethical and aesthetic culture, the management staff should show unity in words in all the work they do, - self-criticism, in general, it is said that they should be exemplary in following advanced human and moral norms.

Keywords: eadership personnel, honesty vaccine, reforms, New Uzbekistan strategy, personnel training, civil society, state administration, moral norms, professional activity, moral-aesthetic culture.

Today, one of the urgent tasks is to educate the leaders on the basis of honesty vaccine. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyov, stated, "Today, life itself requires us to organize the public service system more efficiently, to form professional and fast structures in this direction as well. From this point of view, the task of educating honest personnel who understand the goals and objectives of our reforms, who will sincerely help our people to implement the strategy of New Uzbekistan, is becoming more and more important [1]. Therefore, it is important to consider the ideological foundations of the development of the moral-aesthetic culture of the leading personnel.

In this regard, a lot of research work is being conducted on personnel training. There is a need for philosophical studies aimed at forming honesty and fair functioning skills in management personnel through the development of ethical and aesthetic culture. The present period - the period of radical change of the civil society in terms of quality, requires from each organization, from each of its members, determined effort, accuracy in evaluating their activities, hard work and self-sacrifice. Special responsibilities are assigned to management personnel. In all their activities, they should demonstrate unity of work, self-criticism, and in general, be an example in following advanced human and moral norms. It is necessary to improve leadership activities, methods and tools in all areas. "It is regrettable to note that many leaders are busy with unnecessary paperwork and fruitless meetings instead of solving the vital problems that the people are waiting for [2]".

Currently, there is a growing tendency to view leadership as a purely professional activity, narrowing it down as an official and a field of official study. "Being a leader today is a difficult, but at the same time, an honorable responsibility. In a democratic society, if the people do not support the leaders, and the leaders do not support the people, the real goal, the peace of the country, the well-being of the people, and living with confidence in the future will remain a problem. Unfortunately, in our time when we see complex and turbulent situations

happening in the surrounding countries, the issue of rational and skillful management remains very urgent [3].

In recent years, after long debates, specialists who study the issues of this field are trying to interpret these concepts differently in the form of "an official and a person performing a management function" (dolzhnostnoe litso i litso, vpolnyayushchee upravlencheskie funktsii) [4].

To date, a number of works on the selection of leading personnel have been created, and we can note them as works directly related to management culture, and at the same time as scientific-theoretical, practical-educational sources. In these works, the issues of selection of leadership personnel are covered in different ways. Some of them analyze this process in connection with the socio-political, economic and cultural-spiritual development process of the society, while some of them show it as a unique program covering a set of principles related to the selection of leading personnel and selection for leadership. Therefore, according to the approach to the issue, scientific and theoretical sources can be divided into two groups. The first is direct sources, in which the issues of choosing a leader or being selected for leadership are covered as comprehensively as possible. The second is indirect sources. They include opinions recorded by different people and different works, and although they essentially express views on leadership, they give more information about the spirituality and moral characteristics of the leader. Examples of artistic creations are mentioned as such sources in most cases.

A leader must manage people, a team, that is, he is distinguished from others by his leadership qualities. He is in front of everyone's eyes in the labor team and society, he solves problems related to work and life, and if necessary, the fate of his subordinates. Therefore, he has more responsibility towards others. In this sense, responsibility is the main criterion in the training of modern managers, and it is necessary to be firm in the fulfillment of this duty. What is the criterion of responsibility in this sense? In general, what is management and what are the leadership skills in it? In this sense, justice is the first condition of management and the responsibility of a modern leader. The criterion of justice is not to separate from the people and satisfy their appeal. Failure to be fair in one's work indicates the lack of responsibility of the leader. Because the injustice of the leader leads to the moral violation of people, the decline of society and the loss of faith in the future. What can happen if the leader violates the criterion of justice while the struggle for building a just society is going on?! For this reason, being just is defined in the holy books as the nature of a person. Calling white white and black black, telling the truth and working with the truth is justice. Thus, the second condition of the leader's responsibility is to be a leader in the literal sense. Leadership is about staying one step ahead of people and being able to see and live with tomorrow's prospects and challenges. This can be called having a strategic goal.

According to O'. Shakarov, personnel management is divided into three main types. First, it is organized for centuries with the help of human intelligence, subordinated to cultural traditions, that is, naturalized and unwritten rules; secondly, with the help of directly appointed responsible persons; thirdly, with the help of written documents such as laws, manuals, regulations [5]. Personnel management, formation, training is carried out by people on various social bases through "systematized" or "organizational structure". "Structure" - according to A.N. Leontev, is orientation, planning, implementation and control based on the goal, motive, behavior [6]. Therefore, everything that is not part of the "organizational

structure" and does not affect it, or vice versa, is not affected by the structure, is its external environment. Personnel management means not only regulation, but also goal-oriented, organizational-economic, social-psychological characteristics of the organizational structure with a level of influence.

Management activity, like any activity, performs its tasks based on a number of principles. Based on the principles of management, it is necessary to pay special attention to the selection of managers for the management system [7]:

- democratization and humanization of the process of selection of leaders;
- systematicity and uniformity of the process of selecting leaders;
- transparency and equal rights in the selection of leaders;
- harmonization of state and public cooperation in the selection of leaders;
- objectivity and completeness of information in the selection of leaders.

In the process of building a democratic, legal state and civil society in the new Uzbekistan, what kind of people are in leadership positions in the state and society management system, their spirituality is important. The leader not only participates in the management of the state and society, but also serves as an example to the subordinates, in particular, the subordinate management staff. Therefore, the training of a leader is a matter of great importance. Therefore, it is necessary to start training a leader at the lowest level. Therefore, it is advisable to start work on this at the first stage of education. It was the idea of forming a new generation of leaders along with bringing up a new generation in general. Therefore, high spirituality and culture are also important in the concept of a leader. This was not only a requirement of the transition period, but also a factor that significantly renewed the concept of a leader who could provide the great future of Uzbekistan and serve it.

It is no secret that the following negative characteristics remain in many executives who have received education in the bureaucratic system today:

- indifference to people's pain;
- putting one's own interests first;
- selfishness and greed;
- being an obstacle to the development of the country and the well-being of the people in general.

In fact, these are the people who adopted the spirit of "selfishness and greed" of the leaders of the former regime. Since these negative trends were noticed by the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. Karimov, special importance is being attached to the work of retraining and education of the managers who fall into the category of existing paralysis. If we pay attention, the first President of our country promoted the education of the leaders as a whole, without dividing them into any categories. This is a completely new interpretation of the concept of a manager in accordance with modern requirements. In it, only the leading employee should be worthy of his name is a priority.

The society, the nation, will be free of defects, first of all, it will start with the leaders being able to adapt to the demands of the times, and getting rid of their moral defects. A modern leader should be able to be a leader, selfless, role model and role model for his team with all his qualities.

At the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, the training of modern management personnel requires a scientific approach, taking into account the objective situation. The process of training managers in Uzbekistan has a programmatic basis and consists of a

continuous system of a number of activities, such as selecting talented students of Uzbekistan, improving their knowledge, and forming their professional skills. Thus, specific criteria have been developed in Uzbekistan for the training of modern managers and they are being put into practice. These criteria are consistent with modern management methods and democratic principles of leadership.

Today, leaders, especially heads of enterprises and organizations, should be better aware of the requirements of scientific and technical development, on the one hand, and the need to carry out educational activities in each labor team, on the other hand. When appointing young professionals to leadership work, it is necessary to take into account their organizational ability, participation in ideological and educational work, and their maturity in terms of moral responsibility. They are required to increase their qualifications, work in new labor teams relying on public creativity and show initiative themselves. People often associate all the positive and negative aspects of their real life with the leader's personality. Needless to say, there is a certain correlation. There are many examples of how old-fashioned leaders who care less about creating an atmosphere of high responsibility for the fate of creative research and community-state obligations have failed and dragged whole communities back. Unfortunately, they still exist today. Some business leaders lack long-term strategic goals. He cannot imagine the future of the company he leads. Such leaders replace hard work with narrow practicality, and creative entrepreneurship with false arrogance. Needless to say, how harmful this style is. All this prompts a deeper study of the conditions that make the selection and training of personnel effective and flawless. A strong, morally responsible leader can listen to someone else's advice, thereby preventing tomorrow's problems.

Today, we attach great importance to the creation of human resources. Every leader considers it his duty to cultivate the reserve to raise his employee from the bottom to the top. How deeply he feels his duty and task is determined by how carefully he prepares personnel who are able to replace him at a certain time. In order to further improve the experience of the selection of employees, the personnel included in the reserve should feel that their work and abilities are valued, that if they work actively and conscientiously, they can hope for the support and assistance of the higher authority and promotion in the service path. After all, in the new Uzbekistan, the main principles of the personnel policy put forward by the head of state are required to be applied to the civil society without deviation. It is the sacred duty of all of us to clearly and thoroughly implement this requirement into life. In the socio-economic and spiritual development of our republic, meticulous intelligence, leadership with a clear understanding of the work leads to success. Taking care of this should be one of our main and important tasks.

Indolence, laziness in people has a great impact on the labor process, as a result of which some people advance, and the other part lags behind. This also causes new problems for managers. Achieving the final result of socio-economic reforms in places, bringing the started work to an end, forming a new worldview in people, constitute the core of the tasks before us.

While the presence of leaders with old ways of thinking and old ways of thinking was not felt at the beginning of the reforms, as the reforms deepened and social views in the society moved towards renewal, the need for a new worldview to manage people began to be felt.

It was natural that the process of reforms being carried out in the country, the changes taking place in the life of the society, would create new responsibilities for the leaders.

Therefore, for a manager, initiative, selflessness in introducing the experience of advanced work culture, knowing the mood of people, living with their anxiety, creating new jobs, ensuring the spiritual and material well-being of the people are raised to the level of the main criteria.

In conclusion, it can be said that the introduction of modern management methods is a means of increasing the moral responsibility of managers. The following successes can be achieved if the moral responsibility of the managers of the enterprise or organization, as well as the management staff in general, is increased:

first, to democratize management methods on the basis of legality;

secondly, to introduce team management instead of administrative command management in enterprises and organizations.

thirdly, to increase the moral responsibility of managers in management.

fourthly, all these activities require constant updates.

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